

Poison, Production, and Power: The Anti-Baboon Campaign in Colonial Northern Nigeria, 1945–1959

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Abstract

This article argues that the anti-baboon campaign in colonial Northern Nigeria was not simply a technical response to crop damage but a coercive project of environmental governance shaped by developmental priorities, transimperial knowledge exchange, and contestation from African communities whose livelihoods were endangered by vermin control. Focusing on the Northern Regional Production Development Board and related colonial institutions between 1945 and 1959, it shows how baboons were recast as economic enemies within a wider regime of agricultural production, wildlife regulation, and border surveillance. Drawing on archival, scientific, and press sources, the article demonstrates that baboon control depended on toxic infrastructures, trained poisoners, and publicity campaigns, yet repeatedly generated resistance, compensation claims, and ecological unease that exposed the limits of colonial power. In doing so, it contributes to histories of empire, conservation, and human-animal relations by showing how vermin control linked violence, expertise, and local negotiation in late-colonial Nigeria.

Introduction

This article examines how colonial authorities in Northern Nigeria transformed baboons from recurrent agricultural raiders into targets of an organised campaign of extermination. It argues that anti-baboon policy was not merely a practical response to crop loss: it was part of a broader late-colonial effort to discipline landscapes, secure agricultural production, and extend state authority through wildlife regulation, chemical control, and local surveillance. In tracing this campaign, the article also shows how African community leaders, herders, healers, and farmers did not simply absorb colonial policy but contested its risks, costs, and ecological consequences.

The article intervenes in the historiography of colonial conservation and environmental control in Africa, which has more often centred on game preservation, forest policy, or charismatic

fauna than on the violent management of so-called pest species.¹ While scholars have examined locusts, quelea, rodents, and insects in relation to agricultural loss, the history of baboon control in colonial Nigeria remains largely unexplored.² By drawing together archival records from Nigeria and Britain with scientific and newspaper material, this study reconstructs how colonial expertise framed baboons as economic threats, how techniques of poisoning and publicity were operationalised, and how local actors responded when vermin control endangered cattle, therapeutic practice, and everyday mobility.

Colonial officials developed an eradication campaign that sharply reduced baboon populations in parts of northern Nigeria.³ Although scholarship on agricultural pests in colonial Africa has concentrated on locusts, quelea, rodents, and insects, larger crop-raiding animals such as baboons and elephants have received far less attention. In northern Nigeria, officials repeatedly described baboons as a major threat to crops and seedlings across Plateau, Bauchi, Adamawa, Zaria, Bornu, Kano, Katsina, Sokoto, Niger, and Benue Provinces.⁴ Other primates also damaged crops, but archival records consistently represented baboons as responsible for the most extensive losses.

The analysis proceeds in three moves. First, it shows how colonial officials and development agencies defined baboons as a threat to production and folded vermin control into wider projects of agricultural improvement, conservation, and border management. Second, it reconstructs the practical machinery of extermination, including the circulation of sodium arsenite, the training of poisoners, and the mobilisation of Native Authority institutions. Third, it examines the frictions produced by these policies: livestock deaths, compensation claims, opposition from local actors who relied on wildlife, and growing doubts about the safety and

¹ See Sandra Swart, *Riding High: Horses, Humans and History in South Africa* (Johannesburg, 2010); William Beinart, "African History and Environmental History." *African Affairs* 99, 395 (2000): 269–302; Roger Blench, "A History of Domestic Animals in Northeastern Nigeria." *Cahiers des Sciences Humaines* 31, no. 1 (1995) 181–237; Ingold, Tim, "From Trust to Domination: An Alternative History of Human-Animal Relations." In Aubrey Manning and James Serpell (eds.), *Animals and Human Society: Changing Perspectives* (London, 1994); Darcy Ogada, Darcy, "The Power of Poison: Pesticide Poisoning of Africa's Wildlife". *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 1:2 (2014) 1-20; Saheed Aderinto, *Animality and Colonial Subjecthood in Colonial Africa: The Human and non-Human Creatures of Nigeria* (Ohio, 2022), pp 181-3; David Pratten, *The Man-Leopard Murders: History and Society in Colonial Nigeria* (Edinburgh, 2007); Martin, Kisch, *Letters and Sketches from Northern Nigeria*. (London, 1910); Herbert C. (Johnny) Hall, *Barrack and Bush in Northern Nigeria* (London, 1923).

² W.A. Lamborn, 'The Agricultural Pests of the Southern Provinces, Nigeria' *Bulletin of Entomological Research*, vol. 5 no. 3 (1914) 197-214; J.O. Adejuwon, 'Pests and diseases'. In J.S. Oguntoyinbo, O. Areola and M.O. Filani (eds.), *A Geography of Nigerian Development* (Ibadan, 1978). Aderinto, *Animality and Colonial Subjecthood*, pp 181-3, highlighted the use of sodium arsenite to poison baboons accused of destroying farms.

³ Damage to Crops by Insects, Birds and Baboons (Nigeria National Archives, Kaduna – hereafter NNAK, AGR/21).

⁴ Baboons Method of Destruction of, 11 June 1951" (NNAK, MAHFR 54/1927 vol. 1).

efficacy of mass poisoning. Several documents in the Nigerian National Archives in Kaduna and the National Archives in Kew make it possible to trace both the ambition of the anti-baboon campaign and the limits of its implementation.

These concerns emerged within a wider colonial push to raise agricultural output, protect livestock, and stabilise rural production. Baboons regularly raided millet, bananas, sweet potatoes (*Ipomoea batatas*), maize (*Zea mays*), sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*), guinea corn, beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta*), rice, and groundnuts (*Arachis hypogaea*) in farming zones bordering woodland and savanna. Officials repeatedly noted that fields near forested or rocky areas were especially vulnerable. The scale of reported losses made baboon control a recurring administrative priority in districts such as Pankshin, Shendam, Eggon, Jemaa, and parts of Bauchi and Adamawa.⁵

Crop damage also followed seasonal patterns. Officials reported peaks in maize raiding just before harvest, especially in July and August and again in February and March, while cassava was more vulnerable when maize was unavailable, usually from October or November into early March. These rhythms reinforced the view that baboon control was an urgent matter of agricultural timing rather than an occasional nuisance.

The colonial government expanded control measures in response to repeated complaints from farmers and agricultural officials about crop losses and wider disruption to rural production. Because farming and cattle rearing were economically and politically central to northern Nigeria, officials treated baboon destruction as a problem with implications beyond individual fields.

Initial control efforts relied on shooting, trapping, and bounty payments. In some districts, officials organised hunting parties with local participation, while farmers also guarded fields during weeding and harvest, using spears, slings, fires, fencing, nets, and scarecrows to deter raids. These methods had a limited effect. Officials repeatedly complained that baboons avoided snares, circumvented netting, and returned to fields and storage areas with notable persistence.

Officials also used publicity and mobile campaigns to persuade rural communities that baboon control served agricultural improvement. Yet these measures did not resolve the problem. As

⁵ Baboons Method of Destruction of, 11 June 1951" (NNAK, MAHFR 54/1927 vol. 1).

confidence in guards and hunting waned, the campaign shifted toward more coercive forms of wildlife control and social intervention, especially mass poisoning.

Long before the formal anti-baboon campaign, farmers across Hausaland and other parts of northern Nigeria used seasonal drives, traps, and snares to protect fields from wildlife. These strategies could reduce crop losses and sometimes supplied meat for households, but primates were not always targeted in the same way, especially where they were regarded as non-food animals. Colonial wildlife legislation therefore intersected with, and sometimes displaced, existing local practices of protection and resource use.

Archival material on wildlife administration in Nigeria stretches back to the early twentieth century and shows that colonial officials increasingly treated animal management as a question of law, science, and state authority. In the post-war years, this administrative framework enabled baboon control to be folded into wider debates about conservation, agricultural productivity, and rural order. The anti-baboon campaign thus belongs not only to the history of pest control but also to the history of how colonial rule classified certain animals as legitimate targets of eradication.

A 1950 report to the Director of Commerce and Industries noted that large numbers of leopard skins were passing through Kano depots, prompting some officials to speculate that the decline of leopards might be contributing to baboon population growth.⁶ On that basis, some recommended giving leopards protected status to limit crop damage by baboons and reduce animal movement across the Nigerian, Chadian, and Cameroonian borderlands.⁷ The evidence for this ecological assumption, however, was weak. Contemporary observers themselves acknowledged that leopards might prey on young baboons but were unlikely to control baboon populations in any systematic way.

Even so, official concern about predator loss and animal movement was tied to wider anxieties about cattle security, crop damage, and changing settlement patterns in frontier districts such as Jemaa and Adamawa. Colonial correspondence linked these pressures to rising baboon numbers, even when the underlying causes remained uncertain.⁸ What matters here is less

⁶ Eric Walker for SNP to the Resident, Plateau Province, 3 Oct. 1950 (NNAK, AGR/21).

⁷ Eric Walker for SNP to the Resident, Plateau Province, 3 Oct. 1950 (NNAK, AGR/21).

⁸ A.D.O. Wamba Division to the Resident, Plateau Province, 19 Oct. 1950 (NNAK, AGR/21); C.R. Niven to SNP, 28 Nov. 1950 (NNAK, AGR/21).

whether officials diagnosed the ecology correctly than that such claims helped justify more interventionist forms of vermin control.

Britain and France responded with discussions about cross-border veterinary and game control. Some district officials favoured tighter limits on leopard shooting through licensing, while others regarded leopards as too dangerous to protect. Resident C.R. Niven, for example, dismissed predator protection as a solution and argued instead that officials should attack baboons directly, whether by poison or bacterial means.⁹ Such disagreements reveal that the campaign was shaped not by a single coherent ecological doctrine but by competing views about risk, security, and administrative expediency.

Officials ultimately presented cross-border cooperation as a pragmatic response to the movement of baboons and other animals across frontier zones. The archival record suggests that vermin control was closely tied to surveillance, mobility control, and the management of agricultural space.¹⁰ When baboon colonies were identified in Plateau Province in 1949, for example, officials treated the area as a control hotspot. Training schemes for poisoners, including courses for Native Authority personnel and specialist instruction linked to British expertise, further show how baboon control became institutionalised within late-colonial governance.

Sodium Arsenite

By September 1950, officials had inaugurated a poisoning campaign in Plateau Province using sodium arsenite. Surplus stocks originally held for anti-locust work were redirected to baboon destruction after newer chemicals replaced arsenite in locust control. Correspondence among provincial administrations shows that access to arsenite, and the logistics of moving it, quickly became central to the campaign's expansion.

Reports from 1950 and 1951 described poisoning in Bauchi and Adamawa as effective enough to encourage wider adoption. At a June 1951 meeting of the Provincial Development Committee in Jos, officials agreed that poisoning water holes with arsenite should continue, provided precautions were taken to reduce danger to people.¹¹ District councils were tasked

⁹ D.O. Jemaa Division to the Senior Resident, Plateau Province, 20 Oct. 1950 (NNAK, AGR/21); C.R. Niven to SNP, 28 Nov. 1950 (NNAK, AGR/21).

¹⁰ Resident, Plateau Province to the Resident, Borno Province, 23 Oct. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21); SNP to all Provinces except Ilorin and Plateau, 18 Sept. 1951; Director of Agriculture, Kaduna to the Agricultural Officer at Riyom, 24 Dec. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21).

¹¹ SNP to all Provinces except Ilorin and Plateau, 18 Sept. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21); Minutes of the Provincial Development Committee, 21/22 June 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21).

with organising hunts, and six men were to be sent to Bauchi after the farming season to learn the method. In Jemaa, Mr Tupper Carey trained local poisoners, and officials estimated that four trained men would need at least eight hundredweight of sodium arsenite to cover the division, at a projected cost of £179:4:0.¹²

The importation and circulation of sodium arsenite were governed by the Pharmacy Ordinance, which classified it as a scheduled poison and restricted its import and sale to licensed dispensers, registered chemists, druggists, and certain permit holders. Even so, arsenite entered Nigeria duty-free under a customs exemption, was imported by firms such as John Holt & Co. (Liverpool) Ltd., and was moved internally by transport companies including Messrs Arab's Transport.¹³ These administrative arrangements formed part of the toxic infrastructure that made large-scale baboon control possible.

Funding posed an immediate constraint. District councils complained about crop damage and were willing to contribute, but officials also regarded arsenite purchases as a strain on Native Authority funds. Because successful baboon destruction was expected to raise output, some proposed seeking a £200 grant from the Regional Production Development Board, while others suggested drawing on Agricultural Department stocks or subsidies.¹⁴ The discussion shows that vermin control was framed as an investment in production, even as officials struggled to finance it.

A Table of Stocks of Sodium Arsenite Based on Provincial Returns

Province	Location	Quantity	Remarks
Zaria	-	13 Drums of 56 lbs. each.	5 Drums required for local campaigning
Bornu	-	58 Drums of approximately one cwt. each.	-
Kano	Kano	98 Drums of 1 cwt. each	It will take some considerable time and expense to concentrate in Kano for movement from the Province
“	Districts of Kano Province	25 Drums of 1 cwt. each	“

¹² SNP to all Provinces except Ilorin and Plateau, 18 Sept. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21); D.O. Jemaa Division to the Senior Resident, Plateau Province, 17 July 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21);

¹³ John Holt & Co Ltd to the Secretary, N.R.P.D.B., 7 May 1954 (NNAK, AGR/21).

¹⁴ N.C. Gibbon, Director of Agriculture Northern Region to the Agricultural Officer at Riyom, 24 Dec. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21).

“	Hadejia	4 ¹ / ₂ small tins	“
Adamawa	-	35 Drums	25 in stock, 10 expected shortly from Kabba
Katsina	-	12 Drums of 60 cwt. each	-
Sokoto	-	141 Drums of 1 cwt. each	-
Kabba	-	28 ¹ / ₂ Drums	-
Niger	-	62 Drums = 6,500 lbs	Required for Local Campaign
Benue	Wukari	8 Drums = 908 lbs	-
“	Keffi	9 ¹ / ₂ Drums = 578 lbs	-
“	Nassarawa	13 Drums = 919 lbs	-
“	Lafia	10 Drums = 550 lbs	-
“	Makurdi	13 ¹ / ₂ Drums = 735 lbs	-
Bauchi	-	8 tons 3 cwt	Required for Local Campaign

Source: N.C. Gibbon, Director of Agriculture, Northern Region, to the Agricultural Officer at Riyom, 24 Dec. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21).

By 1954–55, arsenite allocations for Plateau Province were calculated less as a total requirement for eradication than as an estimate of what Native Authority poisoners could realistically deploy. This distinction matters because it suggests that officials were calibrating supply to administrative capacity rather than assuming that complete extermination was feasible.

Sodium Arsenite for Baboon Destruction in Plateau Province

Jos Division	56 lbs
Pankshin Division	56 lbs
Jema'a Division	56 lbs
Southern Division	56 lbs
Lowlands Division	56 lbs
	2 ¹ / ₂ cwts.

Source: Agric Superintendent Plateau to the Acting Resident, Plateau Province, 6 Oct. 1954 (NNAK, AGR/21).

Poison Bait

Baboon destruction relied on two main techniques: poisoned bait and the poisoning of water holes. Officials generally considered the second method more effective because it required less skill, but it was also markedly more dangerous. Where baboons could be denied access to shared water sources, poisoners sometimes fenced water holes and set out alternative containers of poisoned water. Even in official descriptions, however, the method appears as a hazardous

technology of control that threatened people, livestock, and non-target predators alongside baboons.¹⁵

Poison bait demanded more local knowledge and improvisation. Officials reported that baboons were highly selective in what they ate and became wary after repeated attempts, forcing poisoners to adjust food types and timing to local conditions. They also stressed the need to recover and destroy uneaten bait, partly because accidental human contact was a known risk. One archival example describes a man who unknowingly picked up poisoned maize from a path and escaped harm only by chance.

Poisoners also reported practical problems with arsenite itself. A newer, blue-coloured stock appeared less effective than an older colourless version because, once mixed, the bait turned bluish-grey and was thought to arouse baboon suspicion.¹⁶ To test this problem, Capt. H.D. Tupper-Carey experimented with both stocks in the same area. The records do not conclusively establish the issue, but they do show how field practice and local observation shaped the campaign's methods.

Local Incentives and Participation

Payment systems varied by district. In Bauchi Division, poisoners received monthly wages but were required to produce a minimum number of baboon tails; in Gombe, payment was made per tail. Officials regarded the latter system as more effective where communities cooperated in locating carcasses, since baboons often died away from the poisoning site. The evidence underscores how extermination depended not only on chemicals and expertise but also on labour incentives and local participation.

Officials presented the campaign as highly successful, and reports from Kuka, a village between Shendam and Kalum, were used to exemplify that claim. According to a report by T.W. Bonser and Ignatius Dan Baki, two water holes used daily by baboons were identified, nearby hamlets were warned, and rewards of 2d per tail were offered. Within hours of poisoning, carcasses began to appear, and by March 1952, some 450 tails had been handed in.¹⁷ Officials calculated that the poison used cost about 15 shillings, making each recorded kill cost

¹⁵ Resident, Bauchi Province to the Residents of Adamawa, Plateau, Benue and Bornu, 8 Nov. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21).

¹⁶ Baboons: A method of destruction of by H.D. Tupper-Carey, Forest Estate Officer at Bauchi, 8 Oct. 1951 (NNAK, AGR/21).

¹⁷ The National Archives (TNA) London - John Holt & Co files, official debates, memoirs, conservation reports, agricultural reports and surveys held at the National Library of Nigeria, Arewa House Archives in Kaduna and the British Library.

less than 2¹/₂d. In the Eggon Resettlement Area, meanwhile, the campaign intensified in the hills to support wider resettlement and farming schemes.¹⁸ By February 1953, officials reported roughly 800 baboons killed, with additional uncounted deaths assumed.¹⁹

Resistance, Compensation, and Ecological Unease

Baboon control reshaped livelihoods as well as landscapes. The poisoning of water holes with sodium arsenite killed cattle and sheep alongside baboons, exposing herders and farmers to new risks created by the campaign itself. These accidents raised practical questions about warning systems, compensation, and official responsibility, especially in regions crossed by pastoral routes and seasonal movement.

The campaign intensified pre-existing tensions over access to land, water, and wildlife. Crop raiding by baboons imposed serious economic costs on rural communities, but the methods used to suppress baboons also generated new conflicts by exposing people, livestock, and shared resources to toxic danger. Resistance to the campaign therefore emerged not only from sympathy for wildlife but also from the unequal burdens imposed by colonial control.

The campaign's collateral damage is clearest in the compensation record. In March 1953, for example, two Fulani herders received £50 after losing eighteen cattle and six sheep that drank from a poisoned water hole. Officials marked contaminated sites and instructed Native Authorities to notify village heads and Fulani chiefs, but these precautions were unevenly effective, especially given pastoral mobility and the uneven circulation of information. When doubts arose about whether herders had been adequately warned, token compensation was sometimes paid in the interest of preserving local relations, revealing both the administrative limits and political sensitivities of the campaign.

The records also point to emerging ecological and ethical unease. Although the archives do not provide a sustained ecological analysis, they do show growing concern about the wider consequences of mass poisoning and the brutality of available methods. From mid-1954, officials began asking whether a less horrible means of killing baboons could be found.²⁰ By 1955, safety fears had intensified after an accident in Biu Division, and in 1956 the mistaken

¹⁸ Appendix C: Eggon Resettlement Scheme, (NNAK, AGR/21).

¹⁹ District Officer Lowland Division to the Resident, Plateau Province, 3 March 1953 (NNAK, AGR/21).

²⁰ Secretary N.R.P.D.B to the Resident Plateau Province, 10 Sept 1954 (NNAK, AGR/21).

poisoning of twenty-four cattle in the Lowlands Division led local authorities to halt supplies of sodium arsenite for baboon control.²¹

Conclusion

The anti-baboon campaign in colonial Northern Nigeria reveals how vermin control operated as a form of late-colonial environmental governance rather than a narrowly technical response to crop loss. By combining toxic chemicals, trained personnel, Native Authority mobilisation, and cross-border coordination, colonial officials attempted to subordinate animal movement, agricultural risk, and rural livelihoods to developmental priorities. Yet the campaign's history also shows that this project was unstable: baboons adapted, livestock were poisoned, compensation disputes multiplied, and local communities challenged both the methods and the assumptions that underpinned extermination.

The campaign also exposes the uneven reach of colonial authority. Officials could circulate poison, impose regulations, and intensify surveillance, but they could not prevent baboons from moving across the Nigeria–Cameroon border or pastoral communities from following established patterns of cattle mobility. Where baboon control achieved more durable results in the late 1950s, it did so not through coercion alone but through wider local cooperation, including the involvement of community-based animal health workers and greater acceptance among pastoralist communities. Even then, the suppression of one agricultural threat did not produce lasting stability: as baboon numbers declined in some areas, officials increasingly identified elephants as a new danger to crops and rural production.

Taken together, these dynamics reveal the contradictions of colonial rule. Anti-baboon policy depended on local cooperation even as it endangered local lives and livelihoods, and it framed extermination as improvement even when its effects were partial, coercive, and ecologically disruptive. The history of baboon control therefore contributes to the histories of empire, conservation, and human-animal relations by showing that campaigns against so-called vermin were not peripheral to colonial governance but central to the making—and unmaking—of state authority in Africa.

²¹ The National Archives (TNA) London - John Holt & Co files, official debates, memoirs, conservation reports, agricultural reports and surveys held at the National Library of Nigeria, Arewa House Archives in Kaduna and the British Library.